

One Deity, Three Temples: A Typology of Sacred Spaces in Hariyar village, Tharparkar (Sindh)

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Abstract

The landscape of Hariyar village is dotted with many sacred spaces which include temples of Malhan Devi, Thans of Mauji or Rani Bhatiyani, Manbhan varan, Gogo Chauhan, Samadhi of Kesar Puri, memorial stones of Hario Jago and Sonaras. The cults of Malhan and Mauji are widespread in Tharparkar. Firstly, the paper will discuss typology of sacred spaces in Hariyar village and secondly, the temples of Malhan who are worshipped by Hindu castes of the village. There are three temples of Malhan Devi in the village which are erected by Jaga Rajputs and Meghwars respectively. There are also memorial stones in Hariyar Village which are a tribute to the 'unsung heroes and heroines' of Hindu mythology. This article deals with various sacred places- temples, thans and memorial stones of Hariyar. It also discusses a story of the fight between the Sonaras and Jagas which is still narrated by the Maganhars of Mithi town.

Introduction

In recent years emotional connections to places and symbolic qualities of objects and places have received increased attention (Rapoport 1970, 1976, 1982a, b; Relph 1976; Duncan 1985; Altman & Low 1992). The sacred places may be identified by the presence of a solitary mature tree, a spring or unique geological structure rising towards the sky. The sacred spaces are marked by stone piles, hedges or sometimes clay brick structures. Sacred spaces are believed to have special properties that help infertile couples to have children (O'Brien et al 2012).

Sacred objects include sacred texts, *dhoop* (incense sticks), incense stick holders, camphor, wicker baskets for keeping fresh flowers to be used in daily *pooja*, silver and brass vessels for offering food and water to the deities. Mazumdar and Mazumdar (1993) have identified three types of ritual acts specifically related to the *pooja* area. They are (a) purificatory rituals (such as bathing, wearing clean clothes), (b) preparatory rituals (picking flowers from the garden, cleaning the floor of the *pooja* area, drawing ritualized patterns) and (c) *pooja* rituals (offering flowers and fruits to the deities, lighting incense and lamps, singing hymns, chanting prayers)

Methodology

This study was conducted in Hariyar village in the district of Tharparkar. The main object of the study was to understand the local perception about various sacred spaces and their role in the everyday lives of the villagers. For this, focus and in-depth interviews were conducted to get data about the various religious sites and spaces in the village. Information about space and place attachment and hierarchy of spaces also came from these interviews. All the sacred sites of the villages were visited and photographed.

Hariyar Village

Hariyar is a populated village in Mithi *tehsil* of Tharparkar district. It is located 22 km east of Mithi town. There are many sacred spaces in the village which play an important role in the everyday lives of the villagers. From *than* (a platform of deities) of *Devi* to a *loharti* of jhujhar (a deified hero) every space is venerated by villagers. It is noted for the temples of Malhan *Devi*, memorial stones and a peculiar way of life of the villagers. The Jaga Rajputs, Mehar Rajputs, Bhils, Sami, Gurera, Meghwars, Nais (Hindus) and Kumbhars (Muslim) reside in the Hariyar village. Maher Rajputs worship Mauji/Rani Bhatiani. They have built *thans* to honour Mauji. Mauji is also known as Rani Bhatiyani. Mata Rani Bhatiyani's real name was Swarup Kanwar who was the daughter of Jogidas Bhatti, a Bhatti Rajput from Jaisalmer district. She was married to Kalyan Singh ji, a Mahecha Rathore chief from Jasol village. Toady her main temple is located in Jasol village in Barmer district in Rajasthan (Bharucha 2003). Apart from Hariyar, shrines of Mauji are found in many villages of Tharparkar district.

The Jaga and Meghwars worship the Malhan *Devi* who holds sway on their everyday behavior. Both Jaga Rajputs and Meghwars have built separate temples for Malhan *Devi*.

Typology of Sacred Spaces in Hariyar

If one looks at a typology of sacred spaces in Hariyar village, the most sacred spaces are the temples of Malhan *Devi*, an incarnation of Durga and his devotee Hario Jago. Inside the temple of Malhan are memorial stones of her devotees which are fixed in the pillars and walls of the temples. These are sacred sub-spaces within a sacred space of temples which are also worshipped by the Hindu community of Hariyar and other nearby villages. These sub-spaces include the *thans* of Gogoji and Malhan (only worshipped by Meghwars) and memorial stones at Malhan Jo Khud. There are three temples of Malhan *Devi* in the villages; two were built by Rajputs and the third by Meghwar community. Third in the hierarchy of sacred spaces is the *marhi* of Kesar Puri which also attracts many devotees every day and the fourth in the order are thans of Mauji followed by Manbhan Varan

and Gogaji. The fifth category of sacred spaces includes the memorial stones of Jaga and Sonaras. All these sacred spaces constitute the pantheon of Hindu community of Hariyar

Temples of Malhan

Before I discuss the temples of Malhan *Devi*, it is necessary to first describe here brief hagiography. According to a legend Malhan was born in 1186 AD in Jhounagarh. Her father Bhersal Parmar was local Raja of the time. Bhersal was unhappy on her birth and managed to throw away her infant daughter. Servant of Bhersal threw the infant Malhan into pot-kiln of Jagu Kumbhar of Janro village in Jaisalmer (India). When Jagu on next morning found an alive girl in burning kiln, he took her with him and made her his daughter, as Jagu had no children. When she grew up, One day while playing with other girls Malhan caught the horse of Raja Bhersal, when was passing through the village. Bhersal asked the girls to give him (his horse) way to go ahead easily. Malhan denied and stopped the horse there. Bhersal on inquiry (from his servant and Jagu kumbhar) found that Malhan is his own daughter. Then Malhan along with Jagu went to (Kohra Jaisalmer) and lived at home of his maternal uncle (Chandar Shaikhar). Chandar forced Malhan for marrying but she refused to obey. Despite Chandar fixed up the marriage of Malhan, thus a bird (*Hans*) came there and Malhan riding on the bird flew/travelled towards the sky and never returned. Jagu then built a temple in village Janro, Jaisalmer; the temple is still there in Janro which is the main temple of Malhan *Devi*. (Varann, D.)

The Kumbhars of Hariyar village has true respect for Malhan temple. During wedding ceremonies in the community, it is a necessary custom for bridegroom to visit and pay respect to Malhan *Devi* in this temple by bowing his head.

There are three temples of Malhan *Devi* in Hariyar village. A first temple which is also the main and oldest temple is located on the Mithi- Chelhar Road (Fig.1). It was believed to have been erected by Hario Jago. This temple is locally called Malhan- Jo- Khud. As discussed above, there are also memorial stones fixed on the pillars and walls of the temples (Figs. 2-4).

Later, in 2006, it was rebuilt by Dani rathi Krishan Kumar of Chelhar village. There is a small shrine of Malhan which was made by Meghwars of Hariyar village. They have kept wooden tablets of Malhan and fixed tridents into the floor of it (Fig. 5). A second temple is located in Jaga Rajput ward of the village (Fig. 6) and the third temple is located in a Meghwar cluster of the village (Fig. 7) which was erected by Meghwar community in 2004.

The devotees of Malhan in Hariyar village still follow the tenets and women do not wear jewellery or ornaments. Their dwellings are made of wood and hay stack. They do not use burnt or unbaked bricks while building the house. Interestingly, not a single house in the village has a gate.

Shrines of Hario

Apart from various memorial stones on sand dune, there is also a memorial stone of Hario Rajput situated east of the sand dune. It is partially a broken memorial stone (Figs. 8 & 9). Only the upper part depicting a rider on the horse is extant. Hario from who sprang Haripota, migrated some centuries back from Janro area near Jaislmer and settled in Mithi where he founded the village by the name of Hariyar. He was a devotee of Malhan *Devi*. The Jaga Rajputs have built a temple of Hario where his memorial stone is found. He is a *kuladeva* (family deity of Jaga Rajputs) who is invoked on a number of occasions whenever there is the birth of a child, or marriage in the family. Newly wedded couples always visit the temple of Hario to get his blessings. Likewise, newly born babies are also brought to the temple of Hario. There are two shrines of Hario, first is located south of 'Lohartin Wari Bhit', where there is his memorial stone and the second at Malhan Jo Khud which was built in 2013 (Fig. 10).

According to a legend Hario was a very pious person. He lived during the reign of Darbrash Sodho in Umerkot (Harijan). It is believed that once drought hit some parts of Tharparkar. There was no water and grass for the cattle to drink and graze. People were migrating to barrage area. Despite of the drought, the cattle of Hario were grazing and drinking water from the village pond. The village pastures were green and the ponds were full of water. People were surprised to see all this. The local people attribute this miracle to his piousness and sainthood. Apart from this miracle, the devotees of Hario also narrated many of his *parchas* (miracles) which he demonstrated from time to time¹.

The tank of Hario, where his cattle used to drink water during the drought, is located near his shrine and south of 'lohartin wari bhit'. The tank was located between two dunes. It is called 'Hario tar marho' from where people can not cut a tree because it is prohibited (oan) by Hario².

Marhi of Kesar Puri

Apart from the temples of Malhan, the shrine of Hario Jago, *marhi* of Kesar Puri is another sacred space in the village (Fig. 11). It is believed that Kesar Puri took *jivat Samadhi* (living Samadhi, buried himself alive). The *marhi* of Kesar Puri is located west of Mata's temple³. There are many

¹ Information shared by Anbhji Jago, bhopo of Malhan Devi temple.

² Information given by Pritam Das Dinani, a retired school teacher.

³ Information shared by Wagh Puri, shivadari of Marhi of Kesar Puri.

marhis of Puri ascetics in Tharparkar. Two of his *chelas* (disciples) Ram Puri and Bhim Puri preached his thought and ideology in Tharparkar. The *samadhis* of both ascetics are located in Mahiyar villages.

The *marhi* of Kesar Puri also attracts many people who do daily *dhop* at his *samadhi*.

Than of Mauji

The *than* (a small informal shrine, open-platform containing image of a deity) of Mauji is located in a Maher Rajput cluster of the village, west of the temple of Malhan *Devi* (Fig. 12). There is a wooden tablet of Mauji which has been placed in *than* by his caretaker.

Mauji's real name is Rani Bhatiyani who was wife of Kalyan Singh, Bhati princes of Jaisalmer. She committed *sati* when she heard about Sawai Singh's (her brother-in-law death) in battle by throwing herself onto the funeral pyre. There are different variants of the narrative. In another narrative, she commits *sati* after the death of her son by fasting. But Komal Kothari, a folklorist of Rajasthan collected a narrative which mentions her commenting *sati* with her brother-in-law. It is believed that she had an affair with Sawi Singh that's why she became *sati* by throwing herself onto funeral pyre. Chaudhari (2009) cites the second story, in which Rani Bhatiyani has an affair and then throws herself on a funeral pyre, as the most common version of the Rani Bhatiyani narrative.

Trembath (1999) argues that this version of the story, though common and popular among the Manganiyars, is in all probability far from the truth. She provides other instances of women performing *sati* for male members of their family other than their husbands and agrees that there may have been some precedence for this account (1999: 220). However, she says that "given the strict codes of behavior" among Rajput women in Rajasthan; it would have been highly unlikely for Rani Bhatiyani to have had an "affaire" with her brother-in-law.

Than of Mauji is sacred space not only for the villagers of Hariyar but also the neighboring villagers who visit the *than* frequently. Local Hindu community swarms the shrine during the mela which is held thrice in a year.

Than of Manbhan

She was a pious lady of a varan family from Dondar village in Nagarparkar and married to Himath Singh Mehar of Hariyar village. She was a follower of Mauji. She was also believed to have established *than* of Mauji in Hariyar village about a one-hundred year ago. Than of Manbhan is

located northeast of Mauji's *than* (Fig. 13)⁴. She is worshipped by Mehar Rajputs and other communities of the village.

Than of Gogo

There is a small *than* of Gogaji at Malhan Jo Khud (Fig. 14). The Nai Hindu community of Hariyar worship Gogaji. It is also one of the sacred spaces of Hariyar village. Apart from Nai community, the other castes also venerate Gogaji when they visit the temple of Malhan *Devi*⁵.

Gogaji, who is also called, Goga Pir and Zahir Pir (by Muslims) are most popular folk deities of northern India (Sikand 2003:165). The cult of snake God Gogaji is also popular among Rajput and non -Rajput castes of Tharparkar. He is worshipped in the form of snake and in his every *than* is placed an image of a snake. Gogaji cures the patients of snake bites in Tharparkar.

Sati and hero Stones

There are a number of memorial stones in Hariyar village commemorating *satis* (widow-burning) and *jhujhars* (headless heroes) (Fig. 15). The memorial stones are located on a sand dune which belongs to Jaga and Sonara caste of Hindus (Figs. 16&17). There are ten memorial stones, all of which are in crumbling condition.

Recently an incident of attempted theft of the stones was reported. Such incidents are not unusual since these memorial stones are stolen and sold at high prices abroad. These 'treasure hunters' have successfully stolen precious stones from every village and it still continues unabated.

The memorial stones of Sonara Hindus were erected to commemorate their heroism. Legend has it that these Sonaras and a man from Maganhar tribe were killed by Jaga Rajputs who attacked their wedding caravan. The wedding caravan of Umbo was heading towards to Rupa Maari in Badin from Ratnagar, Rajasthan. The name of Umbo's fiancé was Son Bai⁶.

The animals were adorned with bells. As the caravan passed by village Hariyar, the sounds of the bells reached the nearby village. Jagas - the devotees of Malhan *Devi* state that Malhan has prohibited the wearing of elaborate jewellery (*Devi oan*) particularly small bells that jingle. Furthermore, Malhan has warned her devotees of the dangers of luxurious life and the importance of simple living, violation of which always brings curse (*Devi sarap*) and bad luck to a violator. Upon hearing the bells, the Jagas demanded women to take off their precious jewellery which they refused

⁴ Information shared by Hukam Singh.

⁵ Information given by Togo Nai.

⁶ Information given by Hashim Maganhar of Mithi Town.

infuriating the attackers⁷. The Jaga Rajputs killed four Sonaras and one Maganhar. In the fight, bridegroom Umbo was also killed. When the news of his murder reached to Rupa Mari, His in-laws took his body to Rupa Mari where her fiancé tied the wedding knot with his dead body and later took him and became *sati*. All other women whose husbands were also killed in the fight immolated themselves with their deceased husbands.

Later, the descendants of the Sonaras erected the memorial stones in the same place where their ancestors and Maganhar fell. Their memorial stones immortalize the lives of women like a Keats' Grecian urn. There are five sati stones in the Hariyar. The names of the satis are Son Bai, Shatra Devi, Chandi Devi, Chaund Devi and Vindi Devi⁸.

All the *sati* stones carry the similar image of *namaskar* (Fig. 18). The memorial stones are divided into two parts the upper containing the image either of sati or *jhujhar* and lower bearing the text that explains the probable cause of death of the *sati* or hero.

Hero Stone of Kesro Maganhar

Sonaras also erected a memorial for Maganhar believing that he also died defending their patrons (Fig. 19). This memorial stone is testimony to the fact that the Maganhar died while serving and defending his patrons, something they took great pride in. The name of Maganhar was Kesro whose father Karo also served the Sonaras. Kesro belonged to Bahudhar lineage of the Maganhar. Bahudhars were famous musicians in Ratnagar (Baloch 2003). They served not only sonaras but also to the Rajputs.

The Maganhar are an ancient caste of Sindh who in the past survived on the patronage of rulers and wealthy merchants. Maganhar are still keepers of family history of their masters. When a child is born in the family of a Sodha Rajput the Maganhar sing songs wishing the child a long life, apart from praising all members of the child's family on the auspicious occasion. They also sing of the heroic deeds of the ancestors of the Sodha Rajputs. When the Samma Rajputs' rule came to an end, some of the families of the Maganhar preferred to call themselves Sammas. Nowadays, these traditional musicians sing at the birth of a child, at marriage ceremonies and on certain other occasions. Usually, they play the *dhol* (drum). The Maganhar and the Charan castes have preserved the oral history of Tharparkar in their chhands (folk-poetry).

⁷ Informatin given by Anbhji Jago.

⁸ Information shared by karo Maganhar of Mithi Town.

Conclusion

Sacred spaces of Hariyar are sites of psychological healing. The therapeutic nature of sacred spaces or shrines leave here important influences in the village 1) Shrine attract more devotees and pilgrims in past two decades. 2) The new shrines also come up. 3) With coming up new shrines, the older shrines also get improved and reconstructed. The new shrine of Malhan was built by Meghwar community in 2004. Likewise, a new shrine of Hario Jago was also built two years ago. Now, there are two shrines of Hario Jago in the village. The old temple of Malhan Jo Khud was also reconstructed in 2006. All other shrines of Manbhan, Gogo, Kesar Puri and Maujiwere have been reconstructed recently.

Reconstruction of the shrines is linked to popularity of place and deity, from local cult to the regional cult. A few *sati* shrines in other villages of Tharparkar, which were earlier worshipped by single caste, has now acquired multi-caste cult. Likewise, Malhan Mata of Jaga, *kuldevi* of Jaga Rajput, is most popular deity of Tharparkar.

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Fig. 1: Malhan Jo Khud rebuilt in 2006

Fig. 2 : Memorail stone at Malhan Jo Khud

Fig. 3 : Another memorial stones fixed on wall of temple

Fig. 4: Memorial stone fixed on pillar of temple

Fig. 5 : Wooden tablets of Malhan at Than of Malhan at Malhan Jo Khud

Fig. 6: Temple of Malhan in Jaga Rajput cluster of Hariyar village

Fig. 7 : Temple of Malhan in Meghwar cluster of Hariyar village

Fig. 8 : Shrine of Hario Jago

Fig. 9 : Memorial stone of Hario Jago

Fig. 10 : Hario temple nera Malhan temple

Fig. 11 : Marhi of Kesar Puri

Fig. 13: Than of Manbhan Varan

Fig. 12: Than of Mauji

Fig. 14 : Than of Gogaji, the snake deity

Fig. 15 : Memorial stones of Sonaras

Fig. 16 : A memorial stone of Jaga warrior

Fig. 18 : Sati stone at Hariyar village

Fig.17: A hero stone of Sonara caste

Fig. 19: Hero stone of Maganhar